

Village Revitalization: A Priority for Creative Tourism Attraction Design in Celuk

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ABSTRACT: This study emphasizes the importance of studies in the readiness of Celuk Village as a tourist village related to the priority of developing creative tourism attractions based on its creative tourism potential, this research uses a qualitative approach through observation, interviews and surveys which are then analyzed using the Analysis Hierarchy Process (AHP). The results showed that the CREATRIP program through the development of creative tourism attraction designs in Celuk village based on the potential and readiness of the village in the form of an AHP model which is a priority is the village tour while the three forms of creative tourism attractions such as: arts and creative events, educational programs, and daily creative activities can be used as a form of supporting tourist attractions in strengthening the brand image of Celuk village as a creative tourism-based silver craft center. The development of the creative tourism attraction design focuses on the socio-cultural dimension that characterizes Celuk village in its development so that it will automatically contribute to the community's economy and environmental arrangement.

KEYWORDS: Revitalization, creative tourism, silver craft, attraction, Celuk

INTRODUCTION

Most of a tourism destination only prioritizes the promotion of natural resources or other attractions even though the basic thing that is important to design from the beginning is to do differentiation that has characteristics that distinguish it from other tourism destinations, one of the important components of a superior destination and being able to compete has Destination brand value (Ashton, 2015). Broadly speaking, the government has a role in tourism development by providing infrastructure not only in physical form but also through cooperation and coordination with the private sector. The policy set by the government is a guide for stakeholders in carrying out their respective roles. The role of stakeholders and key players in tourism development is called the penta-helix which needs each other and collaborates in supporting the development of a destination in Indonesia. As happened during the pandemic, MSMEs became economic drivers to accommodate the process of moving the quadrant from tourism actors to MSME actors through the application of economic digitalization in MSME business practices in various related business sectors (Subawa, 2022).

Sustainability has become a global wisdom found in all development sectors including the tourism sector. One of them is sustainable tourism which is rooted in the sustainable development paradigm which is a positive trend today in the development of tourist destinations that not only leads to economic factors but also leads to the socio-culture of the community and its environment. Revitalization is interpreted as a process to revive something that was previously powerless to become empowered, in this context, tourism revitalization is a development effort carried out by improving the condition and quality of tourism that has been degraded in an effort to create or increase economic value and maintain sustainability (Hartono et al, 2020; Cemporaningsih et al, 2020; Santosa, 2020). The transformation of industrial areas towards a service economy and increasing cultural facilities in post-industrial areas will gradually increase the influence of culture into an increasingly important tool for future regeneration (Arjana et al, 2021; Jannati, 2021). As happened in Celuk village at the beginning of its development as a silver craft industry village and then directed to the development of sustainable tourist destinations. Village revitalization can be done through the development of creative economy-based industries by optimizing the role of local communities through skills and creativity in creating creative products of high economic value by prioritizing local wisdom (Hendrawan et al, 2019; Istiyanti, 2020).

Celuk Village has tourism potential that can be developed into a tourist destination through the development of a tourist village. The designation of Celuk Village as a tourist village was officially issued by the Decree of the Regent of Gianyar Number 707/E-02/HK/2019 with the main tourism potential being silver handicrafts and Wos River attractions. The tourism potential that can be developed in Celuk village leads to special interest tourism such as educational tourism related to the silver handicraft process,

visiting craft galleries or learning to make silver handicrafts, accommodation in the form of living in a silversmith's house (Wisudawati et al, 2018).

Creative tourism offers unique and creative experiences in the form of workshops, classes or tours featuring local art, music and cuisine (Horrocks, 2015; Carvalho, 2023; Forero, 2023). In order to have the creative experiences expected by creative travelers, critical creative elements and innovative content must be integrated. This is due to the importance of co-creativity between tourists and hosts in the development of creative tourism, as well as the importance of interaction with destinations in attracting tourists to maintain their authenticity and unique appeal without undergoing changes, and promoting the growth of creative tourism (Agusdin, 2018; Duxbury, 2019; Richards, 2020; Guo, et.al, 2023). Based on the potential of creative tourism, it is necessary to design well the development design in the form of creative tourism attractions that can provide an authentic attraction for creative tourists

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach with data collection through direct observation, in-depth interviews and documentation. Experts in this research consisted of: Academics, media, village head, chairman of Celuk Design Center, tourism office, chairman of celuk tourism awareness group, entrepreneur/owner of silver art shop. The initial data collection process involved direct observation of the research location, then making contact with each expert regarding their time availability. The results of interviews with each expert were collected and compiled the development of creative tourist attractions obtained then made a survey to determine the priority of creative tourist attraction design through Analytical Hierachy Process (AHP) analysis using expert choice 11 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The development of tourist attractions related to sustainable silver crafts must be based on Tri Hita Karana which is the vision of Celuk village in its sustainability in the aspects of product, people, place and participation. The development of creativity can be applied in various ways such as creative people, creative process, creative product and creative place (Richards, 2011). The creative tourism program based on Tri Hita Karana and the 4 aspects is hereinafter referred to as CREATRIP (Creative based on Tri Hita Karana Philosophy from Product, People, Place, Participation aspects). The design development of creative tourism attractions in Celuk village in the CREATRIP program can be described in the following form:

1. Village Tours are activities that invite tourists to tour Celuk village and introduce the cultural diversity of the artisan community and buildings with Balinese designs, visit the silver craft museum, see traditional and modern silver craft production.
2. Educational Programs is one of the activity programs that can be done in Celuk village for tourists who have an interest and are serious about learning how to make typical Celuk silver crafts. This program can be in the form of how to make silver crafts directly through silver class activities, or for tourists who are more serious about learning through workshop activities.
3. Daily Creative Activities is a special interest activity for tourists who want to know and feel the daily activities of the silversmith community, so that tourists can live directly in the craftsman's house.
4. Arts and Creative Events are creative tourism activities that involve tourists in exhibiting the results of art in the form of silver crafts that have been made.

The four forms of creative tourism attractions are then analyzed and selected as the priority design of creative tourism attractions in Celuk village through the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) technique. The criteria used in determining the priority design of creative tourist attractions based on the theory of planning in the revitalization of Celuk village through the concept of sustainable tourism development and concepts related to creative tourism obtained from several references to literature studies based on the tourism potential owned by Celuk village which is then discussed with experts based on economic, socio-cultural, environmental, human resources, infrastructure, image, security, education aspects. So that the hierarchical structure of creative tourism attraction design priorities in Celuk tourism village can be seen in the following figure.

Prioritization of Creative Tourism Attraction Design in the CREATRIP Program

The results of the AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process) analysis based on all criteria on the determination of priority design development of creative tourism activities in order to revitalize the village of Celuk as a silver craft center in Gianyar regency is consistent with the value of CR 0.02 in accordance with the requirements declared consistent with the value of Consistency Ratio (CR) < 0.1. Based on the results of determining the design priorities for the development of creative activities in the village of Celuk with eigen vector values respectively as follows (1) Village Tour with eigen vector of 0.288; (2) Arts and Creative Event with eigen vector of 0.258; (3) Educational Program with eigen vector of 0.235; (4) Daily Creative Activities with eigen vector of 0.219. Based on these results, the priority design for the development of creative tourism attractions in Celuk village is the village tour as the main priority of development based on the current condition of Celuk village. The next priority is the development of creative tourism attractions with activities in the form of arts and creative events. Then for the next development related to educational programs and daily creative activities developed as supporting creative tourism activities.

Socio-cultural criteria are the main priority criteria that are considered by stakeholders in determining the creative tourism model in Celuk village with the highest eigen vector value of 0.157 then economic criteria with a value of 0.148, image criteria with a value of 0.143, educational criteria with a value of 0.127, human resource criteria with a value of 0.124, environmental criteria with a value of 0.104, security criteria with a value of 0.100 and infrastructure criteria with a value of 0.097. This is in line with the expectations of stakeholders in the sustainability of the cultural heritage of Celuk village in the form of crafts. This shows that the

priority choices given by experts are consistent and feasible by prioritizing socio-cultural criteria as a priority for creative tourism development design in Celuk village. This is in line with the expectations of stakeholders in the sustainability of Celuk village's cultural heritage in the form of silver handicrafts, one of which is through efforts to register intellectual property in the form of Geographical Index (GI) of Celuk village silver handicraft motifs.

AHP (*Analytical Hierarchy Process*) analysis has the main objective as a functional hierarchy with the main input from human perception through the selection of experts related to the development of Celuk village which leads to creative tourism so that based on these results, the selection of experts is proven to understand the situation that occurs related to the revitalization of Celuk village through creative tourism development. Based on input from experts in future development, it is necessary to carry out planning, development and supervision by taking into account the conditions and potential owned and the synergy of all parties involved in the process.

Based on the results of the Analytic Hierarchy Process, the **CREATRIP** program model with the form of creative tourism attractions **village tours** is a priority design for the development of creative tourism attractions that can be developed in Celuk village by focusing on the development of socio-cultural aspects in maintaining authenticity and local wisdom. While the three other forms of creative tourism attractions can be used as a form of supporting creative tourism attractions in the development of creative tourism attractions in Celuk village.

CONCLUSION

Creative tourism development is carried out through the CREATRIP program with the priority of creative tourist attraction design in the context of revitalizing Celuk village which can be developed based on its tourism potential is a village tour by focusing on the socio-cultural side of the community. This strengthens Richards' (2020) statement with the theoretical focus of creative individuals in an area leading to the development of creative areas or places while still focusing on local culture and traditions in maintaining their uniqueness. In this study, it was also found that to lead or maintain the sustainability of these creative places, creative professional management or management is needed in order to improve creative performance.

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